

A STUDY OF THE POSTBUCKLING PATH OF CYLINDRICALLY CURVED PANELS OF LAMINATED COMPOSITE MATERIALS DURING LOADING AND UNLOADING

Dong Wanlin and Huang Xiaoqing
(South China Univ. of Tech., Guangzhou, China)

ABSTRACT

In this paper, Dynamic Relaxation Method is applied to study the postbuckling path of cylindrically curved panels of laminated composite materials during loading and unloading. The phenomenon that loading paths do not coincide with unloading paths has been found. Numerical results are given for cylindrically curved cross-ply panels subjected to uniformly uniaxial compression under two types of boundary conditions. The influence of the number of layers, the panels curvature and the initial imperfection on the postbuckling paths is discussed.

INTRODUCTION

The postbuckling problem of curved laminated panels has been studied in many papers because it takes an important position in engineering practice. Zhang and Matthews have made a series of study on the postbuckling problem of cylindrically curved laminated panels. They studied the bifurcational behavior of cylindrically curved laminates and discussed the nonbifurcational behavior of simply supported cylindrically curved panels with unsymmetric lay-ups under both compressive and shear loading.¹⁻³ The authors studied the effects of initial geometric imperfection on the large deflection buckling of cylindrically curved laminated panels during loading.⁴ However, all of the aforementioned papers have not investigated the postbuckling behavior during unloading. In this paper, Dynamic Relaxation Method is applied to studying the corresponding relation of load and deflection in a complete process of loading and unloading for cylindrically curved panels of laminated composite materials which are ideal or with initial geometric imperfection. The phenomenon that loading paths do not coincide with unloading paths has been discovered, and thereby the physical meaning of load-deflection curves is further revealed.

BASIC FORMULAE

Let the x- and y-coordinate axes be taken respectively along the generatrix and the arc line of cylindrically curved panels with midsurface radius R, and the z-axis be taken in the direction normal to the panels. Assuming that initial imperfection exists in the panels, the total deflection will be the combination of initial deflection w_0 and deflection w caused by load. Thus, the strains of midsurface can be written as follows

$$\epsilon_x = u_{,x} + \frac{1}{2}(w_{,x})^2 + w_{,x}w_{0,x} \quad (1a)$$

$$\epsilon_y = v_{,y} + \frac{1}{2}(w_{,y})^2 + w_{,y}w_{0,y} - w/R \quad (1b)$$

$$\epsilon_{xy} = u_{,y} + v_{,x} + w_{,x}w_{,y} + w_{0,x}w_{,y} + w_{,x}w_{0,y} \quad (1c)$$

The governing dynamic equations of the panel element are

$$\rho_1 u_{,tt} + \mu_1 u_{,t} = N_{x,x} + N_{xy,y} \quad (2a)$$

$$\rho_2 v_{,ttt} + \mu_2 v_{,t} = N_{xy',x} + N_{y',y} \quad (2b)$$

$$\rho_3 w_{,ttt} + \mu_3 w_{,t} = M_{x',xx} + 2M_{xy',xy} + M_{y',yy} + E + F + G \quad (2c)$$

where ρ_r and μ_r ($r=1,2,3$) are fictitious densities and damping factors respectively; subscript t denotes time; E , F and G are

$$E = N_x(w_{,xx} + w_{o,xx}) \quad (3a)$$

$$F = 2N_{xy}(w_{,xy} + w_{o,xy}) \quad (3b)$$

$$G = N_y(1/R + w_{,yy} + w_{o,yy}) \quad (3c)$$

Performing finite-difference procedure to the three formulae of equation (2), and let

$$\mu_1 \Delta t / \rho_1 = \mu_2 \Delta t / \rho_2 = \mu_3 \Delta t / \rho_3 = \mu \quad (4)$$

the iterative formulae for the velocities at each nodal point can be written, such as

$$\dot{w}(i,j),n = [(1-.5\mu)\dot{w}(i,j),n-1 + C(i,j),n-\frac{1}{2}\Delta t / \rho_3] / (1+.5\mu) \quad (5c)$$

where $C(i,j),n-\frac{1}{2}$ is a finite-difference form of the right-hand side of equation (2c).

Similar equations can be written for \dot{u} and \dot{v} . [Eqs. (5a)-(5b) are omitted.]

From $w_{,t} = \dot{w}$, the iterative formula of the displacement w is

$$w(i,j),n+\frac{1}{2} = w(i,j),n-\frac{1}{2} + \dot{w}(i,j),n \cdot \Delta t \quad (6c)$$

Similar equations can be written for u and v . [Eqs. (6a)-(6b) are omitted.]

In the above iterative formulae the bisubscript notation is used. For example, $\dot{w}(i,j),n$ denotes the velocity in z direction at nodal point (i,j) at the time $(n \cdot \Delta t)$.

The method of calculating fictitious densities may be found in reference.⁴ According to equations (1a-1c), the expressions of $\bar{\epsilon}_x$, $\bar{\epsilon}_y$ and $\bar{\epsilon}_{xy}$ can be written, such as

$$\bar{\epsilon}_x(i,j) = 1/\Delta x + \frac{1}{2} |w(i+1,j) - w(i-1,j)| / (\Delta x)^2 + |w_{o,x}| / (\Delta x) \quad (7a)$$

And according to the constitutive relations of the nonlinear classical lamination theory, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{N}_x(i,j) = & A_{11} \bar{\epsilon}_x(i,j) + A_{12} \bar{\epsilon}_y(i,j) + A_{16} \bar{\epsilon}_{xy}(i,j) \\ & + 4|B_{11}| / (\Delta x)^2 + 4|B_{12}| / (\Delta y)^2 + 2|B_{16}| / (\Delta x \Delta y) \end{aligned} \quad (8a)$$

Similar equations can be written for \bar{N}_y , \bar{N}_{xy} , \bar{M}_x , \bar{M}_y and \bar{M}_{xy} . [Eqs. (8b)-(8f) are omitted.]

Taking $\Delta t=1$, then the formulae of calculating fictitious densities at nodal point (i,j) can be obtained, such as

$$\begin{aligned} \rho_3(i,j),n-\frac{1}{2} = & k \{ [\bar{M}_x(i+1,j) + 2\bar{M}_x(i,j) + \bar{M}_x(i-1,j)] / (\Delta x)^2 \\ & + [\bar{M}_{xy}(i+1,j+1) + \bar{M}_{xy}(i-1,j+1) + \bar{M}_{xy}(i-1,j-1) \\ & + \bar{M}_{xy}(i+1,j-1)] / (2\Delta x \Delta y) + [\bar{M}_y(i,j+1) + 2\bar{M}_y(i,j) \\ & + \bar{M}_y(i,j-1)] / (\Delta y)^2 + \bar{E}(i,j) + \bar{F}(i,j) + \bar{G}(i,j) \} n-\frac{1}{2} \end{aligned} \quad (9c)$$

where k is a constant coefficient which may be chosen from .25 to .5 and \bar{E} , \bar{F} and \bar{G} can be written according to the equations (3a-3c):

$$\bar{E}(i,j) = 4|N_x(i,j)|/(\Delta x)^2 + \bar{N}_x(i,j)|w_{,xx} + w_0,_{xx}| \quad (10a)$$

$$\bar{F}(i,j) = 2|N_{xy}(i,j)|/(\Delta x \Delta y) + 2\bar{N}_{xy}(i,j)|w_{,xy} + w_0,_{xy}| \quad (10b)$$

$$\bar{G}(i,j) = 4|N_y(i,j)|/(\Delta y)^2 + \bar{N}_y(i,j)|1/R + w_{,yy} + w_0,_{yy}| \quad (10c)$$

Similar formulae can be written for ρ_1 and ρ_2 . [Eqs.(9a)-(9b) are omitted.]

The damping factor may be evaluated by the method proposed by the authors.⁴ Let ρ_{\max} and ρ_{\min} denote the maximum and minimum value of ρ_r ($r=1,2,3$) respectively, then the damping factor may be automatically evaluated from

$$\mu = c\sqrt{\rho_{\max}\rho_{\min}} / (\rho_{\max} + \rho_{\min}) \quad (11)$$

where the constant coefficient c may be chosen from .025 to .25.

Expressing force and moment resultants as the functions of displacements according to the constitutive relations, the iterations can be carried out to get the solution.

NUMERICAL EXAMPLES

In the examples for computation, the cylindrical curved cross-ply panels subjected to uniform axial compression shown in Fig. 1 have been considered. Here, $a/b=1$, $b/h=100$ and let $K=b^2/(Rh)$.

1. Material Properties

The material properties of the two materials used for computation are listed in Table 1.

Table 1 Elastic constants of composites

Material	E_{11} (GN/m ²)	E_{22} (GN/m ²)	ν_{12}	G_{12} (GN/m ²)
Boron/Epoxy	206.9	20.7	0.3	5.2
Carbon/Epoxy	206.9	5.2	0.25	2.6

Fig. 1

2. Boundary Conditions

Two types of boundary conditions are considered:

A. All edges are movable in-plane and simply supported. Designate it as B1:

$$y=0, b: \quad w=M_y=N_{xy}=N_y=0$$

$$x=0, a: \quad w=M_x=N_{xy}=0,$$

$$N_x=-N$$

B. Loading edges are movable in-plane and clamped, and the other two edges are movable and simply supported. Designate it as B2:

$$y=0, b: \quad w=M_y=N_{xy}=N_y=0$$

$$x=0, a: \quad w=w, x=N_{xy}=0,$$

$$N_x=-N$$

3. Initial Geometric Imperfection

The following initial deflection w_0 is taken as the initial geometric imperfection:

$$\text{For B1: } w_0 = f_0 \sin(\pi x/a) \sin(\pi y/b)$$

$$\text{For B2: } w_0 = f_0 \sin^2(\pi x/a) \sin(\pi y/b)$$

4. Numerical Results

In numerical results the following symbols are used:

- $\delta_0 = f_0/h$ — nondimensional initial central deflection of panels;
- $\delta = w_c/h$ — nondimensional central deflection of panels caused by load;
- $\tilde{N} = Nb^2 / (E_{22}h^3)$ — nondimensional compression.

The results of the computations are summarized in Figs. 2-10:

A. Figures 2-3 are obtained for (90/0) flat plates of boron/epoxy with $\delta_0=0$ and $\delta_0=0.2$ under boundary conditions B1 and B2 respectively. The variation of the central deflection with the increasing and decreasing of uniform uniaxial compression is shown.

B. Figures 4-5 are obtained for (90/0) curved panel ($K=25$) of boron/epoxy with $\delta_0=0$ under boundary conditions B1 and B2 respectively. The loading paths and the unloading paths of the variation of central deflection with the increasing and decreasing of uniform uniaxial compression are shown.

C. Figures 6-7 are obtained for (90/0) curved panel ($K=25$) of boron/epoxy with $\delta_0=0.2$ under boundary conditions B1 and B2 respectively. The loading paths and the unloading paths are shown.

Fig. 2

Fig. 3

Fig. 4

Fig. 5

Fig. 6

Fig. 7

D. The loading paths and the unloading paths for (90/0) curved panel ($K=35$) of carbon/epoxy with $\delta_0=0$ under boundary condition B1 are shown in Fig. 8.

E. The influence of the number of layers and the panel curvature on the load-deflection curve is shown in Figs. 9-10.

Fig. 8

Fig. 9

Fig. 10

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

From the computation and the analyzing of the numerical results obtained, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. From Figs. 2-9 it can be seen that owing to the coupling between extension and bending there is bending of the unsymmetric cross-ply laminated flat plates and cylindrically curved panels as soon as the axial compression is applied.
2. The influence of panel curvature on the load-deflection curve is very pronounced. For (90/0) cylindrically curved panels, when the panels become less curved ($K=0,10$) the phenomenon usually called "snap-through" will not occur, but when the panels become more curved ($K=25,35$) the snap-through will occur.
3. So long as the snap-through occurs the loading paths do not coincide with the unloading paths. In the case of loading, when load increases gradually from zero to the upper critical value the deflection increases suddenly and a jump occurs. In the case of unloading the deflection decreases along a different path and when load decreases gradually to the lower critical value another jump occurs. The phenomenon that loading paths do not coincide with unloading paths implies that there is loss of energy in a process of loading and unloading because a jump of deflection is accompanied with kinetic energy which is converted into heat energy dissipated.
4. So long as the snap-through does not occur the loading path is coincident with the unloading path because the process of converting kinetic energy into heat energy does not take place for this case.
5. From Fig. 10 it is demonstrated that for (90/0)_n cylindrically curved panels, the larger is n, the better is the load-carrying ability of the panels, while keeping the total thickness constant.
6. From comparisons between Fig. 4 and Fig. 6, Fig. 5 and Fig. 7 it is found that initial geometrical imperfections pronouncedly reduce the critical load values and in

clamped conditions this influence is more conspicuous than in simply-supported conditions.

7. The study of this paper reveals that the intermediate portion of the curve between the upper and lower critical points in the load-deflection curves having S-shape characteristic³ cannot be realized in the actual case of gradual loading (or gradual unloading). Taking Fig. 4 as an example, if gradual unloading begins as soon as the uniform axial pressure increasing gradually from zero (point 0) reaches the upper critical value (point A), the load-deflection curve will go down following the path of pre-buckling (from point A to point 0); if gradual loading begins again as soon as the load decreasing gradually from the point C of post-buckling stage reaches the lower critical value (point B), the load-deflection curve will go up following the original unloading path (from point B to point C) again. This assertion may be further corroborated by experiment.

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